

Title: Barriers to Eye Health Access for Older Women (50 -80) in Liberia: A Gender-Specific Analysis employing survey research methodology.

Abstract: Eye health is crucial for maintaining quality of life, particularly for the elderly. In Liberia, older women face a higher risk of blindness, yet their specific challenges in accessing eye health services remain under-researched. This study, with its potential to significantly improve the lives of older women (aged 50-80), aims to fill this gap by identifying and addressing the barriers that prevent them from accessing eye health services.

The survey was conducted across three regions—Margibi, Grand Bassa, and Sinoe County—and involved 132 participants (115 women and 17 men). The findings reveal significant demand-side barriers, including limited financial decision-making power, lack of personal funds, distance and transportation costs, illiteracy, and lack of information. The study emphasizes the urgent need for targeted interventions to enhance older women's access to eye health services, promote women's empowerment, and improve eye health outcomes.

Methodology: A survey was conducted in Margibi, Grand Bassa, and Sinoe County, involving 132 participants (115 women and 17 men) aged 50-80—the study aimed to identify gender-specific barriers to accessing eye health services. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis.

Results: The survey identified several barriers that older women experience in accessing eye health services: Limited financial decision-making power, Lack of personal funds, Distance and transportation costs, Illiteracy, Lack of information

Conclusion: This study provides evidence-based insights into the barriers that older women face in accessing eye health services in Liberia. It underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions and calls for the immediate attention of policymakers, stakeholders, and service providers. By addressing these barriers, eye health services can become more accessible, ultimately improving the quality of life for older women in Liberia.

Additionally, this research highlights the necessity of developing project proposals aimed at promoting women's empowerment through the prevention of blindness. The findings should be utilized by policymakers, stakeholders, and service providers to create effective strategies that enhance access to eye health services for women

Keywords: Limited financial decision-making power, Lack of personal funds, Distance and transportation costs, Illiteracy, Lack of information

Foreword

Firstly, I want to thank God for allowing me to live and making it possible for me to seek knowledge to pursue my career goal. Also, I want to thank the Orange Knowledge Program/ Saxion Student Students scholarship for providing me the opportunity to study a Master's in Business Administration at the prestigious Saxion University of Applied Science.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Access barriers to eye health in Liberia are critical to ensuring optimal eye health services because they mediate the prevalence of blindness. Previous studies in Liberia argue a high prevalence of blindness in age 50 and above primarily due to access barriers. According to the Rapid Assessment of Avoidable Blindness (RAAB) survey report conducted in 2012, there is a high prevalence of blindness in ages 50 years and above. It mentioned access barriers as the leading factor giving eight of the fifteen counties/regions in Liberia have no eye care service (Dolo, 2012). Also, Sendolo (2018) argues that the increasing prevalence of blindness in persons 50 and above each year threatens the Liberian population. Women in remote locations are mostly victims because of social and economic factors limiting their access to eye health centers. We recognized that not many studies had been conducted in this field in Liberia. However, fewer studies only focus on providing side barriers, e.g., quality staff, medical supplies, equipment, etc. Also, it mentioned that those aged 50 and above have a high prevalence of blindness and visual impairment due to access. It did not mention the gender effect to know where the magnitude is comparing men and women.

Moreover, factors describing the challenges persons 50 years and above experience in accessing eye health services are not rooted in understanding what access factors affect the elderly (50 and above). Lately, a study conducted in Liberia to describe the demographic distribution and ocular diagnosis of patients using electronic medical records argues women have less access to eye health than men based on their socioeconomic status (Das et al., 2019). Thus, we now recognize that those aged 50 and above are likely to have blindness and visual impairment due to access barriers, but women of the same age are at significant risk factors because of their socioeconomic status.

Given that the lack of access to eye health services is a significant risk factor for women, it is crucial to know what factors prevent women's access to tackle it. Previous studies show the lack of access experienced by women to eye health care services in developing countries can be attributed to awareness, cultural-social and geographical access barriers (Courtright and Lowella 2006 & 2009). The above barriers can be described in-depth as liberty to movement, financial decision authority, and women not prioritizing eye health as cultural-social barriers. Distance,

transportation costs, and little money of their own Geographical access barriers and illiteracy and information as awareness barriers. While existing literature proves that the above factors have a mediated effect on the high magnitude of blindness among women. These insights into the field must be used as established knowledge to test the situation in Liberia. Therefore, a study aiming to investigate barriers affecting Liberian women aged 50 and above is crucial to understand the specific barrier at play to prevent the high prevalence of blindness in women.

1.2 Overview of Liberia

Liberia is a country located in West Africa. It has a border with Ivory Coast in the East, Guinea on the North, Sierra Leone in the West, and the Atlantic Ocean in the South. The country has around 4 million, with an annual growth rate of 2.1 percent (LIGIS, 2008). We recognized that the World Bank, WorldDimeter.info, and other organizations' population estimates are recent and differ from LIGIS. However, most of the above indexes only focus on cities with a large population, where rural communities are not mentioned. Although the LIGIS statistic is over a decade, it is taken because it is a census and provides detailed information about each county where every town, village, and city is mentioned. So we consider it very vital for the study.

However, the pervasive poverty rate severely affects the population's access to health care, making them vulnerable to diseases and other health-related complications. According to the world bank national consumption report of 2013, 56 percent of the country's population lives below the US\$1.25 per day poverty line. Currently, about 2.1 million people in Liberia live on less than US\$1 per day, while 1.8 million live in what the World Bank refers to as extreme poverty a day (World Bank, 2013). Also, the poverty data reveal deep and rooted inequalities between regions, genders, and social groups. Liberia ranks 177th out of 188 countries on the World Bank's Human Development Index and Gender Inequality Index. Poverty rates are far higher in rural areas than in urban centers, and non-monetary poverty indicators such as access to health care, education, infrastructure, and public services are marked by acute rural-urban and gender disparities. Over 50 percent of Liberian women between the ages of 25 and 34 have not attended school, and the median young woman from a poor rural household has just 1.8 years of formal education (World Bank, 2020). Despite Liberia's significant economic potential, more remote regions remain underdeveloped. This indicates that Liberia's poor economy, poverty, illiteracy, and limited and dilapidated road network pose a severe constraint to women and is likely to affect their access to eye health services.

On the other hand, Liberia's health system has undergone numerous setbacks alongside the economic and demographic challenges mentioned above in the last decade. Although Liberia's health system was on the path to recovery from the 14 years of civil war, the EBOLA epidemic devastated the sector resulting in a recession in the industry (WHO, int. 2021). Not only that, the Covid -19 had a significant effect on the health system and the eye care system, and several units were closed. The eye care system is one of those significant areas affected by this action, resulting in a decrease in eye health utility, which is probable to increase the magnitude of blindness. To date, the eye healthcare industry is not prepared to meet the growing eye healthcare needs because of the economic implications that hamper the national government's efforts to deliver compelling public service, thereby allocating the required budget to meet these eye health needs. The National Eye Health program partners with many international and local organizations interested in preventing blindness; they include Sightsavers, Lion's Club International, One Sight, Help Me See, Samaritan Purse, Rotary Club, and others. These organizations can do more when they are informed of evidence-based research of the eye healthcare needs.

1.3 Statement of the problem

Access to eye health remains life-threatening for the elderly (persons 50 and above), but critical for women. Unfortunately, not many studies in Liberia have given women any attention to signify a higher risk of blindness than men in persons 50 years and above. The rapid assessment of the affordable blindness report of 2012 estimated the magnitude of blindness in Liberia at 0.5%. 4.8% of the estimated magnitude (0.5%) is in age 50 and above, which accounts for the highest magnitude (Dolo, 2012). On top of that, it has gone almost a dicey since the Raabs survey, and principal to the multiple setbacks that the eye health care industry has faced in the past, deduce that the magnitude of blindness in persons 50 and above has drastically escalated and we think the majority would be women. Evidence suggests that in all regions of the world and at all ages, women are significantly more likely to be visually impaired than men (Roger et al., 2017). Also, in Liberia, eye health services are centralized; it is concentrated in the Nation's capital, Monrovia and studies show that few (8 of 15 counties) counties estimated above four thousand (4,000) populations have access to eye health services (Dolo, 2012). The limited eye health facilities would mean that access to eye health services is a major challenge for the majority of the population. Women are a significant risk factor because the majority are illiterate, have poor socioeconomic status, and are challenged with geographical factors (World Bank, 2020). Given that women have little or no

funds of their own to afford their transport and treatment costs (Lewellan and Courtright, 2006) shows that a larger percentage of them are going blind unnoticed. Comparatively, this situation may not be the same for women in developing countries because the gender equity policy provides women the opportunity to be independent. They are in the working class and do not depend on their husband for everything. Furthermore, Kerkulah (2019) mentioned that the required allotment of public funds for advancing the eye healthcare sector is a major problem. Reaching quality eye health services to at least 25% of the urban population and 50% of the rural population to enable their full participation in the growth and development of Liberia is limited. The fact that limited eye healthcare services affect women's eye health-seeking behavior because most are not working (UN Women, Africa, 2019) means that cultural-social factors play a significant role. Studies show that women are primary caretakers of the household, and in most social structures, men's eye care is a priority because they are breadwinners (Lewellan and Courtright, 2006). Globally, studies show that women bear higher burdens of blindness than men. Women are two times more likely to lose their vision than men since husbands in most social structures consent to seek medical care in the household (Lewellan and Courtright, 2006). Also, Roger et al. (2017) argue that women represent about 56% of the world's 36 million blind and 55% of the world's 216.6 million people with moderate and severe vision impairment (MSVI), yet are the least likely to receive treatment as they face both increased risks for developing blindness and barriers to access. Not only do women have more significant needs than men when it comes to accessing eye health care, but they are also accessing those services at a lower rate than men. While women face many of the same barriers as men (e.g., unaffordable direct and indirect costs, fear of treatment, distance to the health facility, etc.), this is often compounded by numerous additional gendered barriers to access, including lack of education; limited decision-making power within their households; poor access to financial resources; and cultural restrictions on traveling and seeking treatment.

The fact that most blindness and visual impairment in older women is due to avoidable causes (WHO, (1999) WHO, IAPB, Right to sight (2020)) goal that no one goes needless blind means that a significant improvement could be made to prevent older women from blindness. However, unless these challenges are tackled, it seems likely that many older women will go blind unnoticed every year. Thus enhance the study to understand the barriers women age 50 -80 experience to access eye health services. We assume that by being aware of those obstacles that prevent women access, we can recommend strategies to remove those obstacles.

1.4 Objectives

This study investigates the barriers to accessing eye health care services experienced by elderly Liberian women in the 50-80 age range as a means to increase women's access to eye health services. It aims to describe factors preventing older women from accessing eye health services in Liberia and recommend strategies to remove those obstacles. By removing those obstacles, more women in the target age range (50-80) will have access, thus increasing revenue and profitability for eye health facilities.

1.5 Main research question

What are barriers to accessing eye health services experienced by elderly Liberian women aged 50 to 80, and how can these barriers be removed to increase access to eye health care services for older women aged 50-80?

1.6 Sub question

- I. What are the cultural-social factors affecting Liberian women aged 50-80 access to eye health services?
- II. What effect do geographical access barriers have on the accessibility of eye health services for Liberian women aged 50-80 to access eye health services?
- III. What awareness factors influence older women on the use of eye health care services?

1.7 Hypothesis and Conceptualization

In previous paragraphs, studies have established that women and men experience the same barriers (some of them at least), but to a different extent. And then, some factors are only relevant for men. Of these, for men, they have zero effect, while for women, they have a large effect, so also, in the case of those, gender is a moderating factor. On the other hand, factors that are only relevant for women will not include gender factors; it is measured by those barriers (geographical access and awareness) to test if they have a large effect on the use of eye health services by women applying the age factor. Therefore, those factors identified as barriers (awareness, geographical access, and cultural-social barriers) will be the Independent variables, and eye health service will be the dependent variable. The Gender factor as the moderating variable will only be applied to cultural-social barriers to test the relationship between male and female opinion. It will also interpret

whether the cultural-social factor is larger among women or not; when the testing shows no relationship, there is a significant effect among women and vice versa.

H0: Gender moderates the effect of cultural-social factors on the use of eye health care services.

H1: Gender does not moderate the effect of cultural-social factors on the use of eye health care services.

H1: The effect of cultural-social factors on eye health care service is larger among women than men.

H0: Geographical access have a large effect on the use of eye care services by older women (5080)

H1: Geographical access does not affect the use of eye care services by older women. (age 50-80)

H0: Women in the age range of 50-80 awareness have a large effect on the use of eye care services.

H1: Women in the age range of 50-80 awareness does not have a large effect on the use of eye care services.

2 Literature review

2.1 Prevalence of Blindness in Women

Blindness is an increasing global public health problem with a gender inequitable magnitude (Siyingwa, 2016). There has been increasing proof that women are affected by blindness and visual impairment to a much greater degree than men. A systematic examination of global populationbased blindness surveys carried out between 1980 and 2000 (Mushumbusi et al., 2021) showed that blindness is about 40 percent more common in women than men (in persons older than 50 years). Similarly, A rapid assessment of avoidable blindness (RAAB) conducted in 2007 estimated the prevalence of blindness to be higher among women over 50 years at 3.4%, compared to 2% of the male population globally (Neyhouser et al. (2018). While the rapid assessment of avoidable blindness (RAAB) conducted in Liberia in 2012 estimated the prevalence of blindness in age 50 and above. There have also been several extensive national surveys (for example, IAPB, Ghana (2015) and Nigeria, 2020) and many rapid assessments of preventable blindness studies (RAABs), which have inveterate the previous results. We now recognize that being a woman is a significant risk factor for some eye diseases; it is also an essential factor in the use of eye care services: women account for 64 percent of the total number of blind persons globally, and also in many areas, men are twice as probable to be able to access eye health than women (Courtright, Mganga and Lewallen, (2011), Resnikoff (2008) and Abou –Gareeb et al., (2001)).

Figure 1, estimated global blindness by gender (2001)

2.2 Barriers to accessing eye health services

The above research proves that women 50 years and above are more likely to have blindness and visual impairment than men in the same age range. The World Health Organization (WHO) Vision 2020 mentioned that the high prevalence of blindness and visual impairment among persons 50 years and above in Africa results from access barriers to eye health services. Also, Lewallen and Courtright (2009) argue that patients who live with blindness and low vision in Africa and Asia do not use eye health services. If patients in these extreme conditions cannot use the eye health service that they need the most, some obstacles prevent them from using eye health services, which are known as barriers. We recognized that the high prevalence of blindness and visual impairment among women in Africa is largely due to access barriers; therefore, it is crucial to understand the barriers from established knowledge as a means to tackle them. Previous studies show that barriers women experience to access eye health can be described in three i. Cultural-social barriers ii. Geographical access barriers and Awareness barriers. Assuming these barriers without knowing the factors at play might not provide an in-depth insight into the problem. Therefore, the incoming paragraphs will elaborate on how these barriers affect older women's access. It will be rooted by describing those factors at play to be tested in the survey.

2.3 Cultural-Social Barriers

Previous studies have described cultural-social barriers as i. Liberty to movement, ii. financial decision-making authority, iii. women's eye health is not a priority in the family iv. women's eye health need not urgent and v. fear about vision loss. Lewallen and Courtright (2009), Neyhouser et al. (2018), and Orza et al. (2017) mentioned liberty of movement and financial decision-making authority as barriers. While Lewallen and Courtright (2009), Orza et al. (2017), Neyhouser et al. (2018), and Orza et al. (2017) mentioned that women do not prioritize their eye health needs as barriers. Additionally, Roger et al. (2017) also provided extra insights from the view of low education levels, which the other sources did not mention as factors associated with liberty of movement. Lewallen and Courtright (2009) mentioned that women's eye health need not be urgent, and Orza et al. (2017) and Lewallen and Courtright (2009) mentioned women's fear about vision being lost as a barrier.

Most sources describe three main topics regarding cultural-social barriers. However, none of the concepts refer to all three topics but rather a different combination of these themes. The three main

topics that describe cultural-social barriers are i. Liberty to movement, ii. Financial decision-making authority, and iii. Women do not prioritize their eye health needs.

On the other hand, women's eye health needs are not urgent and fear of vision loss is not selected because not many sources could account for these factors. Therefore, it is viewed as relevant. The selected factors are reviewed and discussed in the coming paragraphs.

2.3.1 Liberty to Movement

Lewallen and Courtright (2009) argue that in most African cultures, women may not have the liberty of movement because they are primary childcare and household tasks, and their need for eye care may not be measured as urgent or imperative as that of a male family member.

Similarly,

Neyhouser et al. (2018) argue that women's status as primary caretakers has confined them to the household because they are not outgoing people, and sadly, they have less participation in healthcare decision-making in the household. On the other hand, Orza et al. (2017) argue that women's freedom of movement is due to unequal power relationships. While Roger et al. (2017) argue that low literacy levels can be a major obstacle preventing women from identifying and seeking eye health care, women's and girls' status as primary caretakers in the family may prevent them from seeking eye care. Furthermore, women may not see their vision as bad as the clinical examination would present (Neyhouser et al., 2018). For example, women might have a visual impairment and ignorantly think it is something else and may not seek appropriate eye care services until it results in blindness, at which time they have no control over it. Looking at these sources, we see liberty of movement mentioned from different emphases but the same idea from the view of obstacles that affect women's eye health access because of their liberty to move.

2.3.2 Financial Decision Making Authority

Lewallen and Courtright (2009) argue that women are the primary caretakers in the household. It is believed that this role restricts women's movement and affects their financial decision authority in the home because they cannot generate income. Previous studies show that women have less participation in the family's financial decision-making process in most African cultures, which affects their eye healthcare access. According to Roger et al. (2017), men's dominance in financial decision-making in the home gives women a low priority. Moreover, it stops them from

having agency over their own eye health needs. If women are not to generate income in the household, it is evident that they will have less influence on how money is spent, which influences their eye health-seeking behavior because they do not have the financial decision-making power.

Similarly, Neyhouser et al. (2018) argue that women have limited agency in healthcare decision-making, and women might not be able to prioritize their own health as such fees threaten access chiefly for impoverished people. After all, they may not always seek appropriate care or postpone necessary health care consumption because many cannot afford regular eye treatment. At the same time, Orza et al. (2017) argue that women's unequal power relationship is also reflected in the lack of authority affecting access and control of resources that would allow them to move freely.

2.3.3 Women's eye health not a priority in the family

Roger et al. (2017) argue that the low power women experience when it comes to decision-making in the household reflects their eye health priority in the family because they do not decide or control how money is spent. According to Neyhouser et al. (2018), women not being able to prioritize their needs affect their access to eye health services, which is likely to result in blindness and visual impairment. Also, Lewallen and Courtright (2009) argue that women worry about how their vision loss may affect their position in the family, and some may prioritize their family's needs above their own need for eye care. While Roger et al. (2017) emphasize that the role of the husband, other male relatives, social networks, morals, and cultural norms might mean that women's eye health takes lower priority and stop them from having agency over their eye care. Women's less influence when it comes to participation in financial decision-making (Rogers et al., 2017) interpret that they do not have control over their eye health condition because they are not the priority.

Although the above paragraphs use different keywords but emphasize the same, Lewallen and Courtright (2009) mentioned liberty of movement, while Orza et al. (2017) mentioned women unable to move freely, and Neyhouser et al. (2018) women are confined to the household. On the other hand, Lewallen and Courtright (2009) also mentioned financial making authority, Orza et al. (2017) lack of authority and control of resources, and Roger et al. (2017) mentioned decision making authority. Furthermore, Neyhouser (2018) mentioned women's eye health is not a priority in the family, and Lewallen and Courtright (2009) mentioned childcare and household

tasks do not make them prioritize their health. As Roger et al. (2017) mentioned, women are the primary caretakers in the family.

Liberty to movement and women do not prioritize their eye health needs solely focus on women's role in the household while financial decision-making authority focuses on men's influence on the household's role. This study also disproves the notion that women's cultural and social barriers solely focus on household functions.

2.4 Geographical Access Barriers

Previous studies have described geographical access barriers as i. Quality of the road ii. Distance iii. Transport cost and iv. Limited funds of their own. Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2011), Roger et al. (2017), and Peter et al. (2018) mentioned distance and transportation costs as geographical access barriers. While Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2011), Neyhouser et al. (2018) mentioned women have limited funds of their own, and Peter et al. (2018) and Lewallen and Courtright (2011) mentioned the quality of the road as a geographical access barrier.

When looking at these concepts of geographical access barriers, most sources describe three main topics looking at different barriers. However, none of the concepts refer to all three topics but rather a different combination of these themes. The three main topics that describe geographical access barriers are (1) Distance, (2) Transportation cost, and (3) Limited funds of their own. Many sources did not mention the quality of the road, and the view was not relevant for the study. The income paragraphs will provide a detailed review and discussion of the selected sources.

2.4.1 Distance

Distance is a crucial factor that hugely affects the population of many countries in Africa regarding accessing health. Previous studies show that there are limited eye health facilities in many African regions, which are scattered in locations that are not accessible to most of the population. It principally affects older women because of their social and economic status and age factor (50 above), which does not allow them to travel long distances. According to Lewallen and Courtright (2011), the quality of roads and the dispersed nature of the population mean that people must often travel long distances to access care. Both long distances and poor quality roads often result in too high transport costs for the rural poor to afford, which often affects women more because they have limited funds and minimal experience traveling outside of the village.

Also, Roger et al., (2017) argue comparing the actual distance & physical access from eye health services. In particular, this may mean that women in rural areas may have less access to health services than women in urban areas.

Similarly, Peter et al. (2017) argue that distance is the physical distance or travel time from the service delivery point to the user's residence. Likewise, Lewallen and Courtright (2006) argue that distance in traveling from home to eye health care service is provided. Therefore, if eye health services are not accessible, women may not regularly seek eye health even if it is a free service because of the distance.

2.4.2 Transportation cost

In much of Africa and Asia, providing hospital transport is essential for reaching older women in rural areas. However, due to financial, social, and cultural constraints, these women often cannot travel to a hospital to seek services. Also, the limited eye health care providers hugely challenge women because they cannot afford the transport cost. According to Roger et al., (2017), geographical remoteness may affect eye health outcomes due to lengthy travel times, lack of availability of public transport, and high transport costs. In addition, the difficulty of organizing transport, Long distances to the referral hospitals, and lack of disability-friendly transportation or lack of reliable transport may adversely affect women.

Similarly, the rapid assessment of affordable blindness in 2012 argues that limited healthcare centers in Liberia make transportation a major challenge for rural community dwellers aged 50 and above. Also, Peter et al. (2018) argue that Many African countries have two reasons (wet and dry season); during the wet, rainy season, remote areas would mean that you have to spend two times the previous transportation due to bad road and lack of adequate communication service limit access. If the money spent on transportation could be equivalent to treatment cost, women will postpone necessary healthcare consumption (Neyhouser et al. 2018); the treatment cost and transportation cost will be a huge financial burden that will affect their eye health-seeking behaviour

2.4.3 Limited fund of their own

Women's limited funds of their own reflect their role (primary caretaker) in the household. Women in most low- and middle-income countries cannot make individual decisions regarding their health. In most cases, decision-making is the remit of husbands or sons (Lewallen and Courtright, 2006). Women being financially dependent has a trickle-down effect on their regular access to eye health because their husband or children might not always have the means or agree to sponsor their eye health services; Neyhouser et al. (2018) argue that women do not perceive their eye health as bad as the clinical examination will be. We think that it can be attributed to downplaying their eye health condition because of limited funds of their own. Similarly, Lewallen and Courtright (2006) argue many older women depend on their husbands or children to pay their treatment costs; therefore, the absence of their husbands/children will mean no treatment for them. On the other hand, Lewallen and Courtright (2011) argue that women's limited fund also affects their financial capacity to travel distance for eye health services.

A critical look at the above concepts on geographical access, many sources use the same keywords to discuss the topic. The only exception is one topic, limited funds of their own (Lewallen and Courtright (2011), which is viewed the same as a lack of control over household resources, (Neyhouser et al. (2018), and Lewallen and Courtright (2006) view it as women have little money or control over how money is spent. These topics did not solely focus on distance and transportation costs as key geographical access but also mentioned women having limited funds as a geographical access barrier.

2.5 Awareness

Illiteracy and information about eye healthcare is describe. These two factors are discussed interchangeably because of close relationships. Also, many studies have discussed them together but as different variables.

Roger et al. (2017) mentioned that women's low literacy levels could be a major obstacle that prevents them from identifying and seeking eye health care. Women tend to have lower levels of education in rural areas because a strong preference is given for sons. After all, daughters are view as an economic burden. This means that many parents would rather pay for their sons than their daughters to receive education or vocational training – especially when families are poor and their resources are limited; as a result, when daughters reach adulthood, they are less educated less able to earn a living and to be financially independent. Also, Lawallen and Courtright (2006) argue older women have a low education level; therefore, they are unaware that some blindness can be

cured, know where to go, and get there. Language barriers and unfamiliarity with the eye health system can lead to decreased awareness of eye health.

Conversely, health information and information about available eye care services enable mothers to educate their children regarding eye care and eye hygiene. Given that they are not informed that they cannot help themselves and their children prevent blindness, serious attention must be given to women's education and information (Lawallen and Courtright, 2006).

The prevalence of blindness reinforces the urgency for women aged 50 and above because researchers have recognized that the high prevalence of blindness results from their limited access to eye health services. Access barriers in the study are described as cultural-social barriers, geographical access barriers, and awareness barriers. An in-depth analysis of their barriers recognized liberty to movement, financial decision authority, women not prioritizing eye health, distance, transportation cost, limited money of their own, illiteracy, and information about eye health to be key factors at play. These factors are keywords that provide in-depth insight into the problem that will be used to formulate subject questions in the operationalization.

2.6 Theoretical analysis

Lewallen and Courtright (2006) view barriers that affect women at three levels: lack of awareness of services, lack of access to services, and reluctance to accept services". In comparison, Peter et al. (2008) argue that access barriers are timely use of service according to need. Access is maximized by accounting for the four dimensions of access: accessibility, availability, affordability, and acceptability. Also, Lewallen and Courtright (2009) view barriers women experience to access eye health services as principal to two factors: liberty of movement and limited financial decision-making authority in the household.

In the above paragraphs, Lewallen and Courtright (2006) mentioned awareness as a barrier to affect women's access to eye health services which Peter et al. (2018) concept on barriers did not mention. Lewallen and Courtright's perspective focuses on two key factors: women education level and information; given that women are less likely to be educated than men, they are therefore less likely to be aware that some blindness can be a cure, to know where to go, and know-how to get there.

Conversely, Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2009) and Peter et al. (2018) have mentioned geography access as a barrier. However, Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2009) views are definite to a female situation compared to Peter et al. (2018). Lewallen and Courtright (2006) argue that the access barrier women experience is due to distance and cost, given that in many African countries, health facilities are scattered, which makes it difficult for women to afford the distance and treatment cost. Likewise, Lewallen and Courtright (2009) view access from the perspective of women's liberty of movement and financial decisions, given that in most African cultures, men are the breadwinners for the family, and women are caretakers of the home, and that gives men the advantage to make a financial decision in the home. On the other hand, Peter et al. (2018) argue access is the time and distance from the household location to the service location, given that these factors serve as barriers because the distance, cost, and price of service affect household resources, and they are not willing to pay. Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2009) and Peter et al. (2018) have mentioned similar perspectives on distance and cost to address access barriers but different perspectives. However, Peter et al. (2018) differ from the reason for household resources and

willingness to pay, which is a view as a general perspective not directly relating to a female situation.

Lewallen and Courtright (2006) mentioned Reluctance to accept service, while Peter et al. (2018) mentioned acceptability as a barrier to health access. However, the two sources mentioned the exact keywords (Reluctance to accept service and Acceptability) but differed in the argument. Lewallen and Courtright (2006) argue reluctance to serve as a woman's role in the household, which makes her confined to household chores, not permitting her to access eye health services. Peter et al. (2018) argue acceptability is the match between how responsive health service providers are to social and cultural needs and the individual's and users' social and cultural expectations and community. However, Peter et al., (2018) concept of acceptability gives a reasonable account of supply-side barriers that are not the study's focus.

Peter et al. (2008) argue that availability is a barrier to healthcare access, resulting from a lack of trained staff and limited supplies and equipment to facilitate healthcare practice. Although Courtright and Lowella (2006) did not mention anything about availability, Peter et al. (2008) refer to service providers, which is not the focus of the study.

Given the above comparison, Peter et al. (2008) model on barriers to accessing health service is unsuitable for the study because it is a general health model not rooted in the specific female situation the study aims to address. Lewallen and Courtright's (2006) concepts of access are viewed relevant for the study because it is specific to women's situations and provides an in-depth and more substantial perspective of an African culture that can be viewed similarly to the factors of barrier mentioned (geographical access and women cultural-social situation) in previous paragraphs (Neyhouser et al. (2018) and Courtright, Mganga, and Lewallen (2011)). Moreover, Roger et al. (2017) set the foundation of the study. Also, this concept is deeply rooted in the African culture, which is likely to be expected in many Africa countries (Liberia). Given these bases, Lewallen and Courtright's (2006) concept is suitable for this study. See table (2)

Lewallen and Courtright (2006)	Peter et al. (2008)	Lewallen and Courtright (2009)	operationalization (THESE WILL BE THE KEYWORDS THAT YOU WILL USE TO FORMULATE YOUR SUBQUESTIONS AND THE IDEAS THAT WILL COME BACK IN YOUR QUESTIONNAIRE...)	
<u>Awareness</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illiteracy/language barrier • Information 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illiteracy and information
<u>Access</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance • Cost 	<u>Geography access</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • service location • household location <u>Affordability</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cost and price for service • Households resources and wiliness to pay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Access</u> • liberty of movement • financial decision-making power 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • geographical access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance, transportation cost, and limited funds of their own
<u>Reluctant to accept service/Cultural, social factor</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • role of women in the house 	<u>Acceptability</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • characteristic of the health system • user attitude and expectation <u>Availability</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of train staff • limited supplies and equipment 	<u>Cultural-social factors</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • liberty of movement □ urgent • childcare household tasks • vision loss may affect their position in the family • prioritize their family's needs above their own • Fear • Limited financial decision-making power 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • socio-cultural factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • liberty of movement • prioritize their family's needs above their own • limited financial decision-making power

Table 1, Theoretical analysis Table

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research will apply a quantitative methodology because it allows the collection of data sizeable population to test the hypothesis that can be used to assess possible reasons for analysis that will prompt robust strategies to tackle the problem. It was based on desk studies and field study data. The desk study was conducted to search relevant information from various sources such as books, articles and journals, internet searching, and national and international statistics. Data was collected through a nonprobability base convenient sample. The majority of the literature was searched using the Saxion online library, Google Scholar, and Greenwich online library.

The field data were collected from both males and females aged 50 -80 years. Women were in the majority because they were the primary focus of the study compared to men, who were a minority. Males were elected in the data collection to provide a perspective as head of the home to test if their role in the household culturally affects women's access to eye health services (Lewallen and Courtright, 2006). The data collected from respondents is to gather information on the phenomena as a means to tackle the prevalence of blindness among women in Liberia. This claims the researcher's attention given that the research requires testing hypotheses in Liberia to recommend strategies to remove obstacles preventing women's access to eye healthcare services.

3.2 Research philosophy

This research applied positivism philosophy because the research is independent, research conducted is objective, and uses confirmed knowledge to generate and test the hypothesis on the phenomena (challenges elderly women aged 50-80 experience to access eye health services). Positivism philosophy approach is taken because it describes the systematic process of the study. According to Research-Methodology (2021), positivist research is relevant and progresses through hypothesis and deduction; concepts need to be operationalized so that they can be measured and use statistical probability. Moreover, in positivist studies, the researcher is independent of the study, and there are no provisions for human interests within the study. Crowther and Lancaster (2008) argue that as a general rule, positivist studies usually adopt a deductive approach, whereas the inductive research approach is usually associated with a phenomenology philosophy. Moreover, positivism relates to the viewpoint that the researcher needs to concentrate on facts, whereas

phenomenology concentrates on the meaning and has provisions for human interest. Studies show that when you assume a positivist approach to your study, you are independent of your research and can be purely objective.

3.3 Research approach

This study will use an exploratory testing approach because not much insight is known in Liberia on the barrier women experience to access eye health services. Existing knowledge established in the literature review on factors influencing barriers women experience will serve as a testable knowledge to obtaining a good grasp of the phenomena and advancing knowledge through subsequent theory building and hypothesis testing through a survey to accept or reject the concept.

This research will apply a quantitative methodology because it will utilize quantitative data from a questionnaire exploring how women aged 50-80 perceive barriers to accessing eye health services. Research shows that questionnaires with many people might have to be undertaken to handle the situation and understand the phenomena. The quantitative methodology will support the core of this research by providing in-depth insight into the phenomena from the respondent's point of view (Leedy and Ormrod, 2001).

3.4 Research Strategy

The research design is a survey because the study is exploratory, given that it will ask a question to gain insight into the phenomena, as not much is known in the field in Liberia. Also, it is deductive. It is based on established knowledge or theory and is quantitative because it allows the collection of data from a sizeable population that can be used to assess possible reasons for analysis. Research shows that surveys work well with exploratory, deductive, and quantitative designs (Leedy and Ormrod, 2001).

3.5 Methods of data collection

A questionnaire will be a good approach because it provides a relatively cheap, quick, and efficient way of obtaining a large amount of information from a large sample of people (McLeod, 2018). Additionally, a questionnaire can effectively measure the behavior, attitudes, preferences, opinion, and intentions relative to more significant subjects more cheaply and quickly than other methods. Moreover, this suits the research purpose because it is intended to gain insight and opinions from a large number of people. Data can be collected relatively quickly because the researcher would not need to be present, and the interview would not be impractical (McLeod, 2018). This explanation suits the researcher's case because he cannot do the data collection due to his geographical location. His colleagues in New Sight Eye Center will collect data who work on clinical outreaches in urban and rural communities. The outreach team is selected because they carried out eye health programs in communities and have a wide range of knowledge and experience in dealing with patients. Principal to the scope of their work, the researchers believed they could carry out a successful data collection.

3.6 Study area

The data will be collected in three counties' urban and rural communities in Liberia: Grand Bassa County, Margibi County, and Rivercess County. These countries are found in central Liberia and extend to the south, bordering the Atlantic Ocean. According to the rapid assessment of avoidable blindness survey conducted in 2012, the above three counties are classified among the eight of the fifteen regions with no available eye health facilities (Dolo, 2012). The absence of eye health care facilities will mean that people living in these regions have to travel to Monrovia's national capital to access eye health services, which is approximately 101 km for dwellers in Grand Bassa and Margibi; Riverless county location is approximately 135km. These distances are taking into account only during the dry season (Summer). During the rainy season (winter), the duration certainly escalates due to bad road conditions. The Liberia Institute of Statistics and Geoinformation Service (LIGIS) report 2008 shows that the three counties have the highest population among the eight counties classified in the Raabs survey with a lack of eye health care services. Grand Bassa County has a total population of 221,693; Male is estimated at 11,093

(1.998%), Female 110,780 (2.001%). Margibi County has an estimated population of 209,923, Male estimated at 105,840 (1.983%) and Female 104, 083 (2.016%) Rivercess County has an estimated population of 71,509, Male estimated at 37,334 (1.915%) and Female 34,285 (2.085%). The above description provides an ideal situation for the survey to examine the challenges women experience in accessing eye health services.

Fig. 2 Map of Liberia showing the study areas: Grand Bassa, Margibi, and Rivercess County ■
 Also, the map show country with no available eye health service ■ populated counties ■ and
 counties with eye health facilities counties with eye health care facilities (Dolo, 2012)

3.6.1 Selection Criteria

These counties were selected based on purposive criteria, including poverty levels and the unavailability of eye health care providers, as mentioned by the raab survey, 2012 in Liberia. In addition, the three counties were picked from the eight countries with no eye healthcare providers based on high population density. Also, these counties are in the hub in Liberia, which provides an ideal setting for the study. Besides, the researcher has an in-depth knowledge of the eye health situation in the Liberian context because he works with the New Sight Eye Center, One of the largest private eye health facilities in Liberia. The selection was not intended to represent the whole country but rather to provide insight into the barriers of eye health care access for women in a diverse range of settings in Liberia.

3.7 Measurement instruments

A primary online questionnaire will be applied to the study in that it enables the researcher to collect reliable data, which will be later analyzed (Nairaproject.com, 2014). Collecting data from study participants seeks the opinion of individuals in a simple or population on the issue directly related to the study's objective (Anina, 2004, pp. 348). It clearly defines the purpose of the study. The method is enhanced because most of the respondents are illiterate, not exposed to internet-related activities, and may not have any internet device (Phone, tablets, computer, etc.). It means that they cannot answer the questionnaires by themselves. This instrument has no demerit because the questionnaires are short, comprehensible to illiterate individuals, and administered by individuals with knowledge and experience in dealing with the elderly.

Data collection is an essential part of any research activity. The conclusions of the study are based on what the data reveal. Therefore, no researcher is greater than the questionnaire (Nairaproject.com, 2014).

3.8 Operationalization

Cultural-social factors, Geographic access, and Awareness are the three concepts relevant to this study, which measures barriers older women experience to access eye health through an online survey questionnaire. The study uses detailed research questionnaires deeply rooted in these concepts based on the difficulty of accessing questionnaires with comparable scope. The following sub-section provides the details of the research instruments used to measure the variables involved in the study.

Seven variables will be used in the research as an index to measure the barriers experienced by elderly Liberian women age 50 – 60 to accessing eye health care in a twenty-question survey. The researcher uses two statements on the concept of awareness (Lewallen and Courtright (2006), and Roger et al., (2017)). Two statements on the concept of Geographical access (Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2011), Roger et al., (2017), Dolo (2012), and Neyhouser et al. (, 2018)). And three statements on cultural-social factors (Lewallen and Courtright (2009), Neyhouser et al. (2018), Roger et al., (2017), and Orza et al., (2017).

The concept of awareness will be measured in two variables: information and illiteracy. To measure illiteracy, the researcher will ask about the targeted respondent's knowledge of eye care. To measure information, the researcher will ask what channel respondents access information about eye health to test older women's awareness of eye health.

The concept of Geographical access will be measured using three index variables: distance, transportation cost, and Limited money women have of their own. To measure the distance, the researcher will ask about the distance from the household to the eye health service. The variable on transportation cost will ask about transportation costs from the household to the service provider. Finally, limited financial decisions will ask who pays the service cost for the elderly to determine if geographical access is a problem.

The cultural-social situation women experience to access eye health will be measured using three index variables: liberty to movement, limited financial decision-making authority, and women's eye health not being prioritized. To measure liberty to movement, the researcher will ask what women's roles are to determine if it confines them to the household. Second, limited financial

decision- the researcher will ask women to seek consent from the husband before spending money in the home. Finally, women's eye health is not being prioritized; the researcher will ask why women's eye care is not a priority home to gain insight into their opinion.

These variables will be measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 2(disagree), 3(Neutral), 4 (agree), and 5(strongly agree). Also, multiple-choice scaling will be used to provide knowledge of distance and transportation costs and measure education level.

3.9 Operationalization of the concepts

Concept	Variables	Items	sources		
Cultural, social situation	Liberty to movement	Taking care of the house and my children does not allow me to leave the house.	Lewallen and Courtright (2009), Neyhouser et al. (2018), Roger et al. (2017), and Orza et al., (2017).		
		I do not think of leaving the house because my husband buys the things needed for the family.			
	Limited Financial Making decision	I need consent from my husband before I can spend any money on the house			
		My husband is the one generating the money; therefore, I do not have control over it.			
	Women Eye Health is not prioritized	Women's and girls' eye health is not prioritized in the home because they are caretakers, not providers.			
		I prioritize household and children's needs above eye health care services.			
Geographic Access	Distance	I cannot access eye health services because of the distance from my residence to the eye health provider.	Lewallen and Courtright (2006 & 2011), Roger et al. (2017), Dolo (2012), and Neyhouser et al. (2018)).		
		What is the distance from your resident to the eye health care location?			
	Transportation cost	I cannot afford the cost of transport from my residence to the eye care provider.			
		How much do you pay for transportation from your residence to an eye health provider?			
	Limited money of their own	My children and family members pay the cost of my eye health service.			
		I do not have money of my own to pay for eye health care services.			
		I do not have control over how money is spent in the home.			
	Awareness	Illiteracy		Eye problems are a family sickness. If any member of your family has them, you will have an eye problem.	Lewallen and Courtright (2006), and Roger et al., (2017)
				Eye problem is a witch that people throw at you.	
When my eye is having a problem, I can use traditional medicine in my eye.					
Information		I do not know where the eye hospital is located.			
		I have not received any information about eye health care.			

3.10 Subject of participants

The study population was conducted in Liberia in three counties (Grand Bassa, Margibi, and River Cess counties). The Liberian Institute of Statistics and Geo-information, in 2008, estimated the female and male population in targeted counties at 503,125. The targeted population (elderly women and men aged 50-80 years) is unknown; the researcher used the nonprobability-based convenience sample technique because it involves non-random selection based on convenience or other criteria, allowing accessible collection of data (Coursehero.com, 2019). Participants who were accessible were selected. Since most of them were illiterate (they could not read), the New Sight Eye Center outreach team's questionnaire was orally conducted.

A sample of 132 participants took part in the survey: men (17) and Women (115), all in the age range 50-80. Fifty-five (55) of the participants were from Margibi, 42 came from Grand Bassa, and 35 were from River Cave County. Therefore, we assume the above sample will represent the population (503,125) with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin error.

3.11 Methods of data analysis

Questionnaires were formulated using Qualtric, which made it accessible to distribute survey questions via social platforms (Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, Linked In, etc.) to collect data. After the field survey, Data was exported from Qualtric to IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for analysis. Collected data was checked and cleaned to ensure maximum accuracy before starting the analysis.

A quantitative technique was employed to use codes that represent keywords or topics conveyed in the survey. These codes bring together participants' responses related to the theme or variable. As part of this step, a univariate technique was used for visual representation on a frequency table, pie chart, and bar chart, while the simple strength was used to calculate the scale (mode, median, mean range, and st. dev.) Tables were created to list the main theme to determine patterns in the data according to source and summarize perceptions on barriers experienced by women to access the use of eye health services. Also, The univariate analysis was used to describe participants' responses based on variables. The three approaches were frequency distribution, a measure of central tendency, and a measure of standard dispersion. At the same time, the bivariate analysis sought to find a relationship between the variables to answer the hypothesis.

3.12 Discussion of Reliability and Validity

Questionnaires are formulated from established knowledge emphasized in the Literature review; they seek opinions from participants on the phenomena to adopt and reject the concept applied in the geographical scope through testing the hypothesis. Also, relevant concepts are operationalized to measure relevant factors employed to the study and how they are applied. These concepts root the research on established knowledge. Data were collected by the New Sight Eye Center Outreach team, consisting of clinicians and ophthalmic nurses who have a wide range of knowledge and experience working in this field.

The researcher will not carry out the data collection, resulting in challenges regarding reliability and validity. However, the researcher will provide education for the data collection team. (New Sight Eye Center outreach team) on data entry from their devices, the reading of oral questionnaire, and questionnaire instruction and application. Clinicians who will carry the data collection process and ensure that every instruction is followed.

Key indicators of a measuring instrument's quality are its reliability and validity; the process of developing and validating an instrument is primarily focused on reducing measurement error. Thus, reliability estimates evaluate the instrument's stability of measures, while validity is the extent to which the results of the interpretation of a test are warranted (Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008).

3.13 Limitations and Ethical Concerns

Some study limitations and difficulties may appear in this research. This paper documents a quantitative study. Quantitative research focuses on testing theories and hypotheses to establish general facts about the topic. The research may result in an incomplete or subjective answer. There may be bias in the information provided by respondents because the focus age group (50-80) responses could be influenced by the circumstances they face. The estimated sample size may not be reached due to bad roads and a low communication network. Respondents may lie due to social desirability (Mcleod, 2018).

Questionnaires are considered intrusions into respondents' private lives due to the time allotted and the sensitivity of the questions asked; a high standard of ethical considerations should be maintained (Quad, 2014).

Quantitative research involves collecting data so that information can be quantified and subjected to statistical treatment to support or refute "alternate knowledge claims" (Wilson and Creswell, 1996). In this study, the researcher was not the person carrying out the data collection, which could lead to some participants skipping questions, leaving incomplete data. A maximum time was allotted to collect data; however, during this period, Liberia experienced the second wave of COVID-19, which led to surrogates having limited time to collect data. This situation also affected the analysis period, as there were time constraints. These challenges were managed by the researcher's guidance of the New Sight Eye Center clinicians, who carried out the data collection process on Qualtrice and ensured that every instruction was followed.

Also, surrogates collecting the data might attempt to answer the question ignorantly by reading it to participants who do not have access to the phone, which might result in bias in answers. This results in challenges regarding reliability and validity. However, the researcher will tutor the New Sight Eye Center clinicians, who will carry out the data collection process on Qualtrice and ensure that every instruction is followed. McLeod (2018) suggests that collecting data is time-consuming and may lead to obtaining a smaller sample size.

4 Analysis and results

4.1 Participants analysis

Table 2 gives an overview of simple participants in the survey. The total number of participants was

(N=132). 17 male and 115 female. Participants came from three counties in Liberia (Margibi, Grand Bassa, and Sinoe). Margibi County accounts for the most participants, 55 (41.6%), 9 male and 46 female, while Grand Bassa County accounts for 36 participants, (27%) 5 male and 31 female. Sinoe County accounts for 35 participants, 17 male and 34 female. Ages were categorized; the highest number of participants was 50-60, which accounts for 44/33.3% of participants. While age 70 -79 accounts for 40/30.3% of participants. Also, ages 60-69 account for 37/28% of participants, and ages 80 and above account for 11 participants only female. Note that the sample's limited number of male participants, as described in previous paragraphs, was attributed to measuring the gender factor only for cultural-social factors among the three factors described in the survey. Therefore, it is not applied to other factors.

				Frequency (N=132)	Percent%
Gender	Male			17	13
	Female			115	87
Counties		Male	Female		
	Margibi Couty	9	46	55	41.6
	Grand Bassa	5	31	36	27.2
	Sinoe County	1	34	35	26.5
Age		Male	Female		
	50-60	8	36	44	33.3
	60-69	4	33	37	28
	70-79	5	35	40	30.3
	80 and Above	0	11	11	8.3

Table 2. Demographic profile

Testing the hypothesis will follow three steps: the visualization of the simple to tell if there exists a relationship in the simple through tables, a measure of association to tell the strength of the relationship in the simple, and the final step would be the testing the hypothesis using an inferential statistic to generalize the relationship in the sample to the total population (503,271). Given that the study employs factors to test three hypotheses, only a strong relationship will be generalized. A weak relation means that it has no significant value for the model.

Measures of association Eta is Interpretation as: $0.00 < \text{Eta } (\eta) < 0.25$: very weak, $0.25 < \text{Eta } (\eta) < 0.50$: weak, $0.50 < \text{Eta } (\eta) < 0.75$: strong, $0.75 < \text{Eta } (\eta) < 1.00$: very strong

4.2. Cultural -social barrier

Three factors (liberty to movement, limited financial decision-making, and women's eye health, not being a priority) are described to test the hypothesis on the cultural-social barrier. Therefore, each of these factors will be analyzed by employing survey questions. Three tables are analyzed: the report table (mean std. deviation range), the Anova table to find if there exists a relationship in the simple, and the Eta measure of association to find the P-value to measure the strength of the relation. If there exists a strong relationship, It will be generalized to the size of the population in the study. This will give a clue to an analysis of cultural-social barriers to rejecting or accepting the hypothesis.

Data Can be Available Upon request.

4.5 Hypothesis and Result

H0: Gender moderates the effect of cultural-social factors on the use of eye health care services.

On average, gender moderates the effect of cultural factors on eye healthcare service; the survey confirms the accepted hypothesis. The survey contained three factors, and questions were formulated to test participants' opinions on cultural-social factors. The three factors are liberty to move, limited financial decision-making, and women's eye health, which is not a priority. Participants rejected liberty to the movement, and women's eye health was not a priority in the household, while limited financial decision-making was accepted. The research analysis proves no relationship between variables and gender in the two cultural-social factors described.

H1: Gender does not moderate the effect of cultural-social factors on the use of eye health care services.

The simple rejects this Hypothesis. The survey data prove there exists a relationship between the variable and gender. Therefore, liberty to movement was accepted as the alternative hypothesis.

H1: The effect of cultural-social factors on eye health care service is more significant among women than men.

The simple in the survey accepts this statement. R analysis proves no relationship between the variable and gender.

H0: Geographical access has a large effect on older women's use of eye care services.
(50-80)

The simple accepts the concept of geography access. The survey analysis proves there is no relationship among the variables. Three factors were used to test the hypothesis; when analyzed, all were found to have no relationship among the variables.

H1: Geographical access does not affect older women's use of eye care services. (age 50-80)

The alternative hypothesis is rejected; there was a relationship among the variables. In addition, participants in the survey agreed with the concept.

H0: Awareness among women in the 50-80 age range does not significantly affect the use of eye care services.

The concept of awareness is accepted; the survey analysis proves no relationship exists among the variables. Two-factor questions were formulated to test the concept of awareness; when analyzed, all were found to have no relationship among the variables.

H1: For women in the age range of 50-80, awareness has a large effect on eye care services. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is rejected. The variables were related, and participants in the survey agreed with this concept.

4.6 Discussion

The research aimed to investigate the barriers to accessing eye health care services experienced by elderly Liberian women in the 50-80 age range to increase women's access to eye health services. This study aims to describe factors preventing older women from accessing eye health services in Liberia and recommend strategies to remove those obstacles. By removing those obstacles, more women in the target age range (50-80) will have access, thus increasing revenue and profitability for eye health facilities.

The survey analysis demonstrates barriers at various steps and how women encounter barriers on their journey towards eye health- from their individual beliefs and attitudes towards eye health to cultural and social barriers in the household and the broader community of economic constraints, distance, transportation cost, information, etc. illiteracy. Overall, the research question was: What are the barriers women aged 50-80 experience to access eye health services? Analysis from the survey informs us of the barriers to accessing eye health: limited financial decisions, limited money of their own, distance, transportation cost, limited money of their own, illiteracy, and awareness. Also, the concept that barriers are prevalent among women aged 50 and above (Dolo, (2012), WHO: Vision (2020), Courtright, Mganga and Lewallen, (2011), Resnikoff (2008) and Abou – Gareeb et al. (2001)). The participants in the survey confirmed this.

4.6.1 What are the cultural-social factors that affect access to eye health

Three factors were described: Liberty to Movement, Limited financial decision-making, and women's eye health not prioritized. These factors formed the cultural-social concept that women often cannot prioritize their eye health because they are housewives and do not generate money in the home. Of these three factors, limited financial decision-making was accepted by participants in the survey. It was consistent with what is known about gender barriers to accessing eye health services in previous paragraphs (Lewallen and Courtright (2009), Neyhouser et al. (2018), Roger et al., (2017) and Orza et al., (2017)). Therefore, we recognized limited financial decision-making as a barrier.

4.6.2 How do geographical access barriers affect the accessibility of eye health services for the elderly?

Geographical access will mean a significant risk for the elderly in the targeted regions (Margibi, Grand Bassa, and Sinoe County) to access eye health. Studies show no eye health is provided in these regions (Dolo, 2012), and dwellers must travel a long distance over 101km. Therefore, the distance, transportation cost, and limited money of their own influence geographical access. The founding of the survey was consistent with what is known about geographical barriers to accessing eye health services in previous paragraphs (Lewallen and Courtright (2011), Roger et al., (2017), Dolo (2012), Neyhouser et al. (2018)). Therefore, if distance, transportation cost, and limited money of their own are addressed, it would remove geographical access among the elderly.

4.6.3 How do awareness barriers affect the use of eye health care services for Liberian women aged 50-80?

The effect of awareness barriers on the use of eye health services is significant; the study identifies these barriers as illiteracy and information about eye health care. Women are more vulnerable to inadequate, inaccurate, or distorted information because they are illiterate, and their primary source of information is word of mouth; vital information on the use of eye health services will reinforce their constant use of eye health services and avoid second-hand details which might not always be true. These factors were examined in the survey and were consistent to what is known as described in previous chapters (Roger et al. (2017) and Lewallen and Courtright (2009)).

The majority of the established knowledge was confirmed in the survey. The two factors rejected were liberty to movement and women's eye health, not a priority. We identify barriers elderly women experience to access eye health, such as Limited financial decision-making, distance, transportation cost, limited money, illiteracy, and information on eye health. The incoming paragraph will elaborate on the recommendation of how these barriers can be removed. Also, this barrier should call the attention of policymaking, service providers, and national and international organizations to women's eye health. If women fail to access eye care services in the early stage of an eye health condition because of the above barriers, they might lose their vision. This will mean that they cannot be productive in the home to respond to their responsibility, which will have a trickle-down effect on their family and society as significant.

4.6.4 Strengths and limitations

The current study adds to the existing evidence because it comprehensively articulates the different barriers and identifies the most significant factors by established knowledge and insight into the opinions of both men and women in urban and rural communities in Liberia. Additionally, the Findings from this study will be an essential tool for WHO Vision 2020, which struggles to incorporate gender issue evaluation because limited available research can help guide the discussion. Also, little study on eye health is known in Liberia; this study provides access to rich information for the eye health care program and valuable data in Liberia's diverse eye health care settings.

This study had some limitations. First, the expected sample size could not be reached because of Liberia's current COVID-19 delta variance. The researcher is confident that future research will elaborate further. Also, many participants could not answer the oral online questions; they live in rural communities and are challenged by the internet and smartphone use. Surrogates may ignorantly influence respondents' responses in an attempt to read the question and answer, which results in bias.

4.7 Conclusion and Recommendation

This study has identified a range of barriers to women in Liberia's access to eye health services. Barriers' experience using eye health services is limited financial decision-making, limited money of their own, distance and transportation costs, illiteracy, and limited information on eye health care. Also, those aged 50 – 70 are significantly at risk because the survey data describe them as the most vulnerable group, and Margibi County was found to be the highest.

4.7.1 How can these barriers be removed?

The first step has been taken: to provide evidence-based research on the barriers women experience to access eye health. Unfortunately, the national government cannot aggressively address these barriers because of its challenges in a poor economy and poverty (World Bank, 2020). In addition, these barriers may have had a more significant effect on women because of their socioeconomic

status (they are not working). Therefore, policymakers, service providers, and stakeholders can use the funding of this research to write/ a project proposal aiming to promote women's empowerment through the prevention of blindness. It will draw the attention of international organizations like Lion Club International, Sight Saver, Samaritan Purse, and One Sight, interested in the eye health program, to sponsor the project. When this project is approved, dwellers in the targeted regions/counties (Margibi, Grand Bassa, and Sinoe) barrier to accessing eye health will be removed. On the other hand, the service providers will benefit immensely because they are implementers, and their health facilities will be used to treat patients with eye problems, increasing revenue for expansion.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Visualization of Operationalization Tree

Researcher

I, Mezo J. Looch, hereby affirm that I have provided comprehensive oral explanations regarding this investigation's nature, methodology, and objectives. I am committed to addressing any inquiries related to the research to the best of my ability.

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